

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: Aqel

FIRST NAME: Ibrahim

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PERIOD NUMBER: P1

INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Kabiru GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references{Citation}The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

My 7 key concepts with the page number in-text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Fundamentals of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Understanding Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-6)
3. Citation guidelines (EUCLID 2019, 6-13)
4. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 24-26)
5. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
6. Chicago Style guide (EUCLID 2019, 44-55)
7. Latin Expressions and Abbreviations (EUCLID 2019, 56-61)

FINDING THE WAY TO ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1)INTRODUCTION

I have recently started my ACA-401D period one course as part of the DIPH program with the study materials of coursepack and video on academic essay writing having in mind some key questions about my personal versus academic writing style, citation and referencing methods, and how to avoid plagiarism?.

Throughout my twenty-five years of working with national and international organizations, I have been using English as my second language in business writing including writing proposals, reports, presentations, and daily business communication. Moreover, I was also able to participate in writing some articles and studies. I used to include many quotations and paraphrases in the articles and studies I wrote without following a specific essay writing style guide. I was always hoping to be able to learn more about the academic essay writing styles in order to improve my writing skills.

In this Response Paper (RP) I am reflecting on the extensive detailed knowledge I have gained to find my way to academic essay writing style, avoiding plagiarism, and differentiate between business writing and academic writing including American and British English (EUCLID 2020, 4). The EUCLID ACA-401D coursepack material and video provided me with not only

answers to my questions but also new skills on how to use Grammarly and Zotero which I have never used before in editing and referencing. I have learned that the academic world is different from the real world, and students need to learn the differences between the two worlds and how the academic English writing differ from real-world English (Levin 2006, 11).

For the past five years, I have been working tirelessly as a leader for one of the largest humanitarian NGOs in Jordan helping refugees and most marginalized populations, providing fair access to sexual reproductive health and sexual gender-based violence information and services as well as supporting related national advocacy efforts for policy change. I envision this program as a window to build my capacity in finding my way to contribute to the regional and international efforts in supporting the rights of the most vulnerable groups, I consider this course as the first step on the ladder.

2) FUNDAMENTALS OF ESSAY WRITING

The first chapter of the ACA-401D period one coursepack explained the basic rules that any researcher should consider when writing an academic essay starting from defining the question that the essay is trying to answer, researching the topic, organizing the ideas, structuring and writing the essay, and editing and referencing it (EUCLID 2019, 1–4).

During my study of chapter one of the ACA-401D period one coursepack, I learned that the non-linearity process of writing an essay means that although there are some basic rules set for guiding the writing process, there will always be a need to revisit what has been written through the different stages of the essay writing process (EUCLID 2019, 1).

I realized that academic essay writing is not about writing all that we can find around a certain topic and structuring the introduction, the body, and the conclusion around it (Norton et al. 2009, 65). Following a style guide and essay writing rules is what I call the hardware of academic essay writing. The writer should also use both creative and critical thinking to develop the essay which I consider as the software of academic essay writing (EUCLID 2019, 2). The hardware of the essay writing process will only help the writer to set the skeleton of the essay which includes following the steps of researching the topic, organizing ideas, writing, referencing, and editing the essay, as well as following a specific style guide. While the software will add the flesh and soul to the skeleton of the essay through employing the writer’s creativity and critical thinking skills to establish a logical evidence-based argument and conclusion.

Through reading this section of the coursepack, I realized how much time and effort the process of writing an academic essay needs and that I will continue reviewing and modifying what I wrote back and forth until the submission of the work following the rule that says “ You haven’t completed your assignment until you’ve handed it in” (EUCLID 2019, 4).

3) UNDERSTANDING PLAGIARISM

Chapter two of the ACA-401D period one coursepack placed the basis for protecting both the work or ideas of authors of previous academic material from being used without being

recognized and the student or writer of the new material from violating other authors' rights (EUCLID 2019, 5).

Ferro and Martins in their paper about Academic Plagiarism: Yielding to Temptation identified four categories of academic plagiarism “using materials from other sources without referencing the source, submitting a paper written by someone else, copying sections of material from one or more source texts, supplying proper documentation but leaving out quotation marks, thus giving the impression that the material has been paraphrased rather than directly quoted, paraphrasing material from one or more source texts without supplying appropriate documentation” (Ferro and Martins 2016, 5).

In my current job, I have been writing proposals and concept notes for different donors to raise funds. Though I used to provide references to the information and statistics used from other sources, I was always wondering whether I have been doing it right and if there were any plagiarism. I have never thought that mentioning the reference without proper citation could be considered as plagiarism. This part of the course helped me to better conceptualize plagiarism in its broader context.

a) Citation guidelines

It was useful for me to learn that using many quotations in an academic essay that does not support or question my argument or provide evidence will weaken my piece of work. Proper citation knowing how and when to use quotations and paraphrases is a key practice to avoid plagiarism. As a student at EUCLID, I learned that I will be using the in-text citation which means citing text taken as quotation or paraphrasing ideas from other's work within my text itself through mentioning the author's name in parenthesis along with the page number that the piece of information was taken from (EUCLID 2019, 6).

The most informative part of this chapter was the paraphrasing guiding notes and examples. I have always found it challenging to explain other author's ideas in my words where I need to keep the idea and change the text (EUCLID 2019, 8-10). The citation format to follow was also very clearly explained and referencing guiding notes were very helpful and direct to the point (EUCLID 2019, 11-12).

While developing this response paper, I had to gain new skills to be able to use the Grammarly check and the Zotero reference manager which I have never used before. This new experience enriched my ability to edit and reference my work. I didn't find any clear guide to help me using Grammarly check and the Zotero reference manager in the ACA-401D period one coursepack or the EUCLID LMS.

4) STYLE GUIDE

Chapter five explained how the style guide shapes the writer's identity and helps him to follow a consistent documentation and writing approach based on the type of writing whether it

was academic writing, technical writing, business writing, or even journalism writing (EUCLID 2019, 24).

I remember using in-text citation during writing my Master's dissertation and my first Ph.D. thesis which was in Arabic language, I was following the university citation and referencing guide which was the Harvard style without having any knowledge about other citation and referencing styles and the differences between them. While I was reviewing on the EUCLID LMS the ACA-401D period one coursepack study material, I found that EUCLID provided access to information about the most common style guides used globally not only the EUCLID selected style which is the Turabian style (EUCLID 2019, 24). It was very useful and informative to me to learn the differences between the Chicago Rules (Turabian style) and the Harvard style. Unfortunately, when I tried to access the other styles on the EUCLID LMS such as the World Health Organization WHO rule of style, the APA rule of style, and the European Commission rule of style, the LMS system did not open any link to the style and instead guided me to the Template for Major Papers. I managed to download them from other websites and it was very useful to go through them.

In general, the takeaway rule for me is that the style guides main purpose is to keep the consistency in writing considering many aspects such as manuscript layout, structure, preferred sentence lengths, font usage, accepted terminology, readership considerations, spelling (British versus American), and citation and referencing (EUCLID 2019, 25).

There are other considerations that I need to take care of when I write to make sure that my piece of work is Grammatically accepted such as knowing when to use a comma, conjunction, apostrophe, or a semicolon. Moreover, I learned that I should focus more on using active voice more than the passive voice (EUCLID 2019, 17, 18, 19).

a) Chicago Style guide

The *Turabian style* as a simplified version of the Chicago Style guide was clearly and professionally presented by Dr. Abel in chapter eight of the ACA-401D period one coursepack. The creative way of categorizing and structuring the Chicago Manual Style CMS Crib Sheet Content into four main categories which consisted of the style & usage, page formatting, end/footnotes, and bibliographies was very helpful for me to logically conceptualize it (EUCLID 2019, 44).

We often do research in our daily life whenever we ask a question and seek answers for it. But not every research is documented and reported supported with evidence and argument to convince others to adopt it or use it (Turabian et al. 2013, 16). In 2013, Kate Larimore Turabian adapted the Chicago Manual Style in its eighth edition to become “A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations” that comprehensively served as one of the most detailed style guides globally (Turabian et al. 2013).

I liked the comprehensiveness of the Chicago Manual Style where it has covered almost all the aspects of writing. On the other hand, the Turabian style is shorter than the Chicago Manual Style and focuses on students rather than publishers, it did not include detailed information about

preparing book manuscripts and journal articles for publication. That's why I appreciated the EUCLID selection of the Turabian style as the recommended style guide.

b) American Versus British English

Chapter six of the ACA-401D period one coursepack sets the rules for using either the American or British English in writing which can be supported through setting the proofing language in the Language section under the Review icon in the Word document.

Despite the fact that the similarities between the American and British English are much more than the differences as both form the World English, there are still some variances in pronunciation of the same spelling and vice versa. In addition to some differences related to grammar, syntax, and punctuation. As well as differences in writing dates, using periods and quotation marks which was clearly described in the coursepack (EUCLID 2019, 27,28,29,35).

c) Latin Expressions and Abbreviations

It was surprising to me to discover that many of the abbreviations I use in my daily work and business communication such as AM/PM, e.g., C.V., etc. are Latin abbreviations that are still used in English writing. The ad hoc, for example, is a widely used terminology in the humanitarian business context that means spontaneous or unplanned but I have never thought that it is Latin in origin (EUCLID 2019, 56,57,59).

This part of the course was an added value to my knowledge about abbreviations usage and Latin English interferences.

5) CONCLUSION

The ACA-401D period one coursepack was very helpful to me in setting the scene for how to start my journey to the DIPH program. I assumed that it will be challenging and overwhelming for me to start a new academic career. I realized the level of complexity and dedication needed to move forward with such an advanced program which thrilled me to become more determined to proceed and challenge the limits. "A person has to remember that the road to success is always under construction. You have to get that through your head. That it is not easy becoming successful"(Akamatsu et al. 1975).

This course tested my writing and citation skills as well as my ability to adhere to the Chicago Style guide as presented by Dr. Abel while writing my first response paper using the CMS Crib Sheet which I appreciated a lot (EUCLID 2019, 44).

I am very grateful to Prof. Cleenewerck and Dr. Gulma for the informative coursepack and video and looking forward to the next challenge in period two of the ACA-401D course.

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